

Two sailors with scurvy described by William Clowes (1596)

by Harri Hemilä

William Clowes was among the leading surgeons of his time. In one of his published works, he described two patients suffering from scurvy; that account is excerpted in this document. Clowes' report is one of the earliest recorded descriptions of scurvy in England.

William Clowes' book was cited in:

Major RH. William Clowes and his "Profitable and Necessarie Booke of Observations".
Ann Med Hist. 1932;4:1-11.

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Lorenz AJ. Some pre-Lind writers on scurvy. Proc Nutr Soc. 1953;12(3):306-324.

<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530062>

Watt J. Some forgotten contributions of naval surgeons. J R Soc Med. 1985;78:753-762.

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Kocher PH. Paracelsan medicine in England; the first thirty years (ca. 1570-1600).

J Hist Med Allied Sci. 1947;2:451-80. [p.474-475]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18919875>

Hughes RE. The rise and fall of the "antiscorbutics": some notes on the traditional cures for "land scurvy". Med Hist. 1990;34:52-64. [p.60-62]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2405219>

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Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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Biographies

“The books of Clowes were the leading surgical writings of the Elizabethan age.”

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Clowes_\(surgeon\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Clowes_(surgeon))

“William Clowes (1544-1604) was probably the foremost surgeon of his age, and certainly few could have had a wider experience of the various aspects of a surgeon’s calling.”

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1940158>

“Thomas Gale succeeded Thomas Vicary as lecturer at Barber-Surgeons’ Hall, and was in his turn succeeded by William Clowes. The latter was Surgeon to Queen Elizabeth and on the staff of St. Bartholomew’ Hospital.”

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1940137>

“William Clowes, senior, was probably the greatest of the Elizabethan surgeons and his books and writings are certainly the best of the Elizabethan age. He wrote on venereal disease, tuberculous glands of neck and burns due to gunpowder.”

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2413942>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7945230>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2479924>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2311518>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5272440>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2413539>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/44449128>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2809172>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/27867638>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.1800155902>

“Clowes ... is generally reputed to be the greatest of the Elizabethan surgeons. This reputation would seem to derive more from the lusty style of his writing than from the technical quality of his surgery.”

Introduction to the 1945 reprint, see at the end of this document

William Clowes. Profitable and Necessarie Booke of Observations.

1596, p.40-43

[https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.\\$b659416&seq=86](https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.$b659416&seq=86) [1945 reprint with Introduction]

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015013724276&seq=80> [1945 reprint, Introduction]

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/s7sjuwds/items?canvas=52>

<https://archive.org/details/b30343719/page/40/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_a-profitable-and-necessa_clowes-wm_1596/page/40/mode/2up

1637 (3rd ed), p.40-43

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.31378008343157&seq=48>

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_a-profitable-and-necessa_clowes-william_1637/page/40/mode/2up

Observations for

The cure of two Seafaring men which fell sicke at the sea of the Scorby.

Cap. 12.

I can not here well passe over this briefe note or obser- p.40
uation of the curing two seafaring men, which trauel-
led a long time upon the seas, and there fell sicke of the
Scorby, which infection as I gathered by inquiry, was
reputed principally unto their rotten and unholosome
victuals,

for they said their bread was musty and mouldie Bisket, their beere sharpe and sower like viniger, their water corrupt and stinking, the best drinke they had, they called Beueridge, halfe wine and halfe putrified water mingled together, and yet a very small and short allowance, their beefe and porke was likewise, by reason of the corruption therof, of a most lothsome and filthy taste and saour,¹ inso-much that they were constrained to stop their noses, when they did eate and drinke thereof: moreouer their bacon was restie,² their fish, butter and chiese woonderfull bad, and so consequently all the rest of their victuals: by meanes hereof, and likewise lacke of conuenient exercise, cleane keeping and shift of apparell, and againe, being in an ill disposed climate, and want of good aire: these causes and such like were the onely meanes they fell into the Scorby, for their gums were rotten euen to the very roots of their teeth, and their cheekes hard and swollen, their teeth were loose nere readie to fall out, their talues³ very painfull, their breath of a filthy saour, that at what time I drest their gums, and washed their mouthes, the saour was so odious,⁴ that I was scarce able to staie and abide it: in like maner their legs were feeble, and so weake, that they were scarce able to carrie their bodies: moreouer, they were full of aches and paines, with many blewish & reddish staines or spots, some broad and some small like flea bitings, or the graines of a Pomegranate, like wise their legs were colde, hard, and swollen, which caused me to fear a Gangræna, for coldnes in such extremities being in corrupt bodies full of euill iuice, both challenge putrifaction, which disease or sicknes, although it be in some safely cured, yet experience daily proueth that a number also die. Now the first thing that required helpe by Chirurgery was their gums, and their legs, being the conioined cause, but for that I will procéede as orderly as I can in my writing, I will begin with the antecedent cause in wardly, which was done and perfor-

1 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/savour>

2 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/restie>
<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/restio>

3 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Talus_bone

4 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/odious>

med by the aduise and counsell of learned Physitions, who very confidently set me dawn their opinions for their maner & order of purging, with other remedies, as hereafter followeth; First as I said, euacuation going before, to diminish the humors sore abounding, it was therefore thought most mète to begin with blood letting in the middle vain on the left arme, & I did then take from ech of them ... ounces of blood. The next day following they were also well purged with this purgation, R_x. ... and herewith they were purged. Also euerie seuenth or eight day they were likewise purged with the pills of Fumitorie⁵ ... made into fine pills, so as I say, after they were well purged, then in the meane space, **there was prepared for them in a readines this drinke following, which continually they did drinke at their meales, and also as often as they were desirous to drinke. The order and making thereof is thus: first there must be prepared a cleane vessell of eight gallons, which was filled full of new ale, and then was added to it of Coclearia⁶ or Scorby grasse a pecke, being purely picked, and cleane washed, and also brused in a stone mortar, and after put into the vessell with the ale,** then was added thereto of long Pepper ... Cinnamon and Ginger of each halfe an ounce, of Saffron ... all these spices were put into a fine linnen cloth or bag, and so hanged in the ale, with the herbes aforesaid, and **thus it rested two daies before they did drinke of it.** And further it is to be remembred, that euery morning they did eate a messe of this Almond milke being newly made, and it did them very much good. R_x. two spoonfuls of French barley,⁷ and sèeth⁸ it in a reasonable quantitie of running water till it be soft, then adde to it of Almonds blaunched ... ounces, **then take of this liquor a pound, and put to it of Coclearia or Scorby grasse, Fumitorie, and water Cresses,⁹ of each halfe a handfull, but first mixe with the Almonds in the beating, of this liquor, for feare the Almonds will turne to an oile, then boile all together to the consumption of the third part, then adde to the straining, of fine Sugar ... of Rose water ... let all these sèeth a little, and then reserue it to your use: In like sort euerie euening towards fower¹⁰ of the clocke they did drinke a good draught of posset¹¹ ale,** whereunto was added of the **iuice of Scorby grasse** a spoonfull, with a little of the powder of Cinnamon and some Sugar, and now and then in stead thereof a good draught of Woormwood¹² wine. Their meates that they did eate was Mutton boiled, and somtimes Weale and chickens, &c.

5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fumaria_officinalis

6 “Cochlearia (scurvy-grass or spoonwort) is a genus of about 30 species of annual and perennial herbs in the family Brassicaceae.” “Scurvy-grass is edible raw and cooked... The leaves are rich in vitamin C.”
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cochlearia>

7 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/barly>

8 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/seethe>

9 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Watercress>

10 Fower. Four.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/fower>

11 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/posset>

12 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artemisia_\(plant\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artemisia_(plant))
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artemisia_absinthium

seasoned with veriui¹³ made of grapes, and thickened with ote meals, or the crums¹⁴ of white bread, with a few Currans,¹⁵ and Raisons of the sunne. Moreouer, there was added of Scorby grasse, Fumitorie, water Cresses, and Soldanella.¹⁶ Their bread was made of the finest wheate, and of a day old. Now hère note you well, that euerie day or second day, one hower¹⁷ after they had receiued a certaine fume, the description hère-after followeth, then they did presently drinke of the aboue named Almond milke. And after their sweating was ended, I did immediately bathe their legs: which done, I annointed them, and lastly I applied a plaister, which hèreafter shall be also nominated. **Now for that their gums were so excèeding stinking and rotten,** I did at the very beginning scarifie their gums with a fleame,¹⁸ then presently I did as it were touch, or wipe their gums gently ouer with a certaine blewish water, which the goldfiners haue used for refining their golde, and haue themselues no use for it, the force and strength being by them greatly consumed and wasted: for the which cause it is called the weake water. After the use hèreof, I did cause them certaine times in the day and in the night, to gargarise or wash their gums and mouthes with my lotion published in my booke for the curing of *Lues Venerea*,¹⁹ Cap. 6. whereunto many times I mixed the ... of Mulberies,²⁰ q.s. also I did at sundrie²¹ times use of the afore named blewish water, and did take thereof ... whereunto I did put of Plantaine water ... and hère with I did mundisse and clense their gums. Also it is knowen most certainly what great good is done in curing of such rotten gums and sore mouthes, onely with this gargarisme, which is published by *Iulius Palmerius*, & it is also set fourth of late by master *Banister* in a booke,²² which he calleth his *Antidotarie Chirurgicall*, R. ...

Also I haue found great good by the use of this powder, which is published by that **reuerend learned man Wyerus,**²³ **who hath written most profoundly for the cure of the Scorby,** take of salt and burne it in a crusible,

13 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Verjuice>

14 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/crumb>

15 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/currant>

16 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Soldanella>

17 Hower. Hour.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/hower>

18 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fleam>

19 Lues Venerea. Syphilis.

https://archive.org/details/b30339601_0001/page/n43/mode/2up Chap. VI.

https://archive.org/details/b30339601_0002/page/26/mode/2up Chap. VI.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.31378008343157&seq=164>

20 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Morus_\(plant\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Morus_(plant))

21 Several.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/sundry>

22 <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/b56562jg/items?canvas=9>

<https://archive.org/details/b30328949/page/n7/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_an-antidotarie-chyrurgic_banister-john_1589

23 Description of scurvy by Wierus (1567).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093229>

whereunto ye shall adde of the powder of Pomegranate flowers, and so mixe them together, & héerwith I did many times rub well their gums. Moreouer, I haue in times past used Vnguentum Ægyptiacum,²⁴ and also a powder called of some Puluis²⁵ Alchimisticus, or Caput mortuum,²⁶ it is the dead head, of Aqua fortis,²⁷ I also after washed their mouthes with vineger and salt water, q.s. and by these meanes I haue cured manie sore mouthes specially in children, when I was Chirurgion unto the children in Christs Hospitall,²⁸ **where I haue had twenty, or thirty infected with the Scorby at a time.** After I had well mundissed²⁹ and cleansed the mouthes and gums of these two men, then I did administer a certaine fume, by the aduice and counsell of D.D. which fume was receiued in at their mouthes by a funnell after this manner, I did take of Mirrhæ, Olibani, Affæ fætidae ana. ... Aceti vinaci ... which gums were grosly beaten, then they were tied loosely in a fine linnen cloth, and so put into the viniger, then there was prepared an earthen pot fit for the purpose, well glassed or nealed, and at those times when it was to be used, there was prepared a funnell made fit in widenes and compasse unto the mouth of the said pot, & so it was well pasted or luted³⁰ together, with this lute called of *Schilander*, and many other good distillers and Alcumists *Lutum sapientie* and it is prooued very necessary to ioine and conglutinate two vessels together seruing for distillations, or otherwise as afore said. R_x. Clay and Fullers haire, with whites of eggs and sand, thus I ioined the pot & the funnel together, and then I set it upon a chaisingdish of coles, and I let it boile gently, & then caused the patients to sit up in their beds one after another, & so they receiued into their mouthes the fume or smoke, that passed forth of the top of the said funnell, & this was used diuers mornings before they did take their Almond milke, and also certaine times in the euening, and did sweate halfe an hower after it in their beds: which fume was administred most chiefly to open their obstructions inwardly, and so being well cooled and dried with warme clothes, they did rise out of their beds, and went to the bathing of their legs, and annointings as followeth, R_x. the flowers of Chamomell,³¹ Melilote³² and Woormewood, the leaues of Coclearia, Water Cresses, and Brookelime, of each a handfull, of the berries of Juniper two handfulls, of Malmsey a quart, running water q.s. swøete³³ butter a pound, these were boiled together, to the consumption of the third part, which bath

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24 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aegyptiacum>

25 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/pulvis>

26 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caput_mortuum

27 https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/aqua_fortis

28 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christ%27s_Hospital

29 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/mundus>

30 Lute was commonly used in distillation, which required airtight vessels and connectors to ensure that no vapours were lost; thus it was employed by chemists and alchemists, the latter being known to refer to it as “lutum sapientie”

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lute_\(material\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lute_(material))

31 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chamomile>

32 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Melilotus>

did bring out in a short time a number of spots, which before lay hid in the flesh, and héerewith very warme, they were a long time together bathed, with double woollen clothes of white cotton or baies, & then dried them very well, with hot linnen clothes: and as I haue before mentioned, they were presently annointed somtimes with Vnguentum Agrippæ, and somtimes with Vnguentum Brioniæ, or Dialthææ cum gum. and also their legs were all wrapped round with this plaister, R_x. Emplastrum Deminio ... Gummi Armoniaci ... being dissolued in Malmsey, then put them together, adding thereto Axungiæ humani ... I boiled these together to the forme of a plaister. I found also very much profit by the Cuminum plaister published in this booke. And thus by the helpe of God and carefull diligence, they were both perfectly cured, and diuers other persons of good account since that time, onely by this maner and order of curing aforesaid, &c.

33 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/sw%C5%93te>
https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/swete#Old_English

Introduction and Medical Introduction in the 1945 reprint.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015013724276&seq=9>

[https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.\\$b659416&seq=9](https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.$b659416&seq=9)

INTRODUCTION

p.iii

The present reprint entitled *A Profitable and Necessarie Booke of Observations* together with the treatise on Lues Venerea is based in part upon two earlier works of William Clowes: *A Short and Profitable Treatise Touching the Cure of the Morbus Gallicus by Unctions* (1579) and *A Prooved Practice for All Young Chirurgions* (1588).³⁴ These books, carefully revised and much augmented, were published together in one volume in 1596 under the title of the work before us. *The Observations* includes sixteen new case histories not found in the *A Prooved Practice* of 1588. Thus *The Observations* of 1596, the last edition published in the author's lifetime, reflects the matured and enriched experience of the author in treating surgical cases and syphilis. For this reason, the editors have chosen to reproduce *The Observations* of 1596 rather than the *A Prooved Practice* of 1588.³⁵

William Clowes, the elder,—whose surname, we learn from the author's verses (p. 137) rhymes with "vowes"—was born about 1540. He lived until 1604 and was one of the best known surgeons in London during the lifetime of Sidney, Marlowe, and Spenser and at the time Shakespeare and Ben Jonson were winning fame as dramatists. The case of the young man (p. 83), a patient of Clowes, wounded in the right eye with a dagger so that "most of the white humor Albumineus issued out of the wound" is strongly suggestive of the manner in which Marlowe met his death, the great difference being that Clowes' patient was cured.

Clowes was descended from Warwickshire gentry, being the son of Thomas and grandson of Nicholas Clowes, both gentlemen of Kingsbury in Warwickshire. We do not know when William Clowes first came to London, but we learn from his *Observations* that he studied surgery as an apprentice of Dr. George Keble, a London surgeon. To Master Keble, the disciple pays tribute in these words:

34 https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_a-prooved-practise-for-a_clowes-wm_1588
https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_a-prooued-practise-for-a_clowes-william_1591
https://archive.org/details/b30329814_0001
https://archive.org/details/b30329814_0002
<https://catalogue.nla.gov.au/catalog/8207353>
<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/e/eebo/A19026.0001.001>

35 Note in the 1945 version:
"For further information on editions and copies of Clowes' writings, see the Bibliographical Note, below."
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015013724276&seq=27>

Surely Alexander the great was never more bound to Aristotle his master for his lessons in philosophie than I was bound to him for giving me the first light and entrance into the knowledge of this noble art of Chirurgerie (p. 183).

As a qualified surgeon, Clowes had a varied and interesting career.

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His active practice began in 1563 in the army commanded by Ambrose Earl of Warwick, in France. After the expedition to France he served for six years as surgeon in the navy. In 1569 he settled in London, and soon became a member of the Barber-Surgeons' Company.³⁶ He was successful in practice, and in March, 1575, was appointed on the surgical staff of Saint Bartholomew's Hospital.³⁷ Here he became a full surgeon in 1581. From time to time in the *Observations* and the *Lues Venerea*, Clowes refers to his experience at Saint Bartholomew's (pp. 149-150).

In May 1585, Clowes gave up his place at Saint Bartholomew's and, at the Queen's command accompanied the Earl of Leicester to the Low Countries. Here he attended, among others, Mr. Crips, lieutenant for Sir Philip Sidney's horsemen (p. 45), and was in the field when Sidney was wounded, though he makes no mention of having attended Sidney. After this expedition, Clowes returned to London and was admitted assistant on the court of the Barber-Surgeons' Company. A few months later he served in the fleet which defeated the Spanish Armada. Though Clowes regrettably gives no details of this particular adventure, one feels that he speaks from fullness of experience when he advises young surgeons what necessary medicines and instruments they should be furnished with when they "follow the wars either by sea or land (pp. 104 ff.)." As "one of hir Maiesties Chirugions" after his return to London Clowes enjoyed several years of successful practice. At the time of his death, in 1604, he was living in retirement, in Essex.

The *Prooved Practice*, referred to above as the first edition of the present reprint, was first published in 1588, with the following title-page:

A prooved practice for all young Chirurgions, concerning burnings with Gunpowder, and woundes made with Gunshot, Sword, Halbard, Pyke, Launce, or such other. Wherein is delivered with all faithfulness, not onely the true receipts of such Medicines as shall make them bolde, but also sundry familiar examples, such, as may leade them as it were by the hand, to the doying of the lyke. Heerto is adioyned a Treatise of the French pockes written by John Almenar

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a Spanish Physitian. Also, a commodious collection of Aphorisms both English and Latin, taken out of an old written cobby. Published for the benefyte of his country, by Wylliam Clowes, Mayster in Chirurgery. Seene and allowed, according to the order appoynted. Printed by Thomas Orwyn, for Thomas Cadman. 1588.

This title-page shows more explicitly than that of the 1596 edition for whom the author was writing; namely, the young surgeons. Though in the latter edition Clowes has

36 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Worshipful_Company_of_Barbers
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1282221>

37 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/St_Bartholomew%27s_Hospital

broadened his appeal, he still keeps steadily in mind the young men just beginning the “noble art of Chirurgery.” With them he seeks to share his knowledge and experience and thus be of greater service to his country.

In keeping with his laudable purpose to disseminate his knowledge more widely, Clowes chose to write in the vernacular.³⁸ For this choice he had ample precedent in the medical treatises of such foreign physicians as Paracelsus, Paré, and Daca Chacon, and in the English writings of Sir Thomas Elyot, Drs. Boorde, Record, Phare, Turner, Bright, Hall, Banister, Cogan, and others. Notwithstanding, Clowes thinks it necessary to defend himself for writing his surgical treatise in English. Some members of the profession, wishing to keep an aura of mystery about the subject, had protested Clowes’ indiscretion of writing in English. In his “Admonition to the Friendly Reader” (p. 221 ff.) Clowes vigorously replies. He regards as absurd the argument that publishing a treatise in English would degrade the art and make it common so that every bad man and ignorant woman might become a surgeon. Clowes urged, as he well knew from experience, that the reading of a book or so on the subject would not make an ordinary man or woman competent to practice physic or surgery. Much more than that is required.

Besides, why should not the true-born Englishman publish books on physic and surgery, in English, as men of other countries had put forth their works in their own language? Hippocrates and Galen wrote in the Greek tongue, Avicen in the Arabian, Plinie in Latin, etc., as Sir Thomas Elyot had asserted thirty years earlier. Calling the roll of English medical writers, as listed above, who had written in the vernacular, Clowes asks:

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Shall all their knowledge, all their painfull labours, and all their commendable works have no better recompence, but a malicious upbraiding, because they are penned in English? O wicked and spitefull minded men, unworthy the benefit of so good labours, not unlike in nature to the Cuckow, which devoureth the bird that brought her up!

As Clowes was one of the best known surgeons of his day, it seems probable that his precept and practice in the use of the vernacular helped to establish the tradition for subsequent writings on medicine and surgery.

Probably the most striking feature of Clowes’ book is his method of presentation. He presents much of his matter in a series of case histories. Of these there were twelve in the earlier work called *A Prooved Practice* (1588). In the *Observations* (1596) this number is increased to twenty-eight, more than double the original. The author is generally specific in stating the name of the patient, the place and time, the nature of the affliction, and the remedy applied. Examples of his procedure may be seen in the case of two gentlemen who were burned while drying gunpowder (p. 2); or the cure of Thomas Gore shot by Dutch soldiers while he was in Flushing, making suit unto the prince of Orange and the States for the release of a ship and goods of his and his friends, which the Flushingers had taken at sea (pp. 6-7); or the cure of John Searle, soldier,

38 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vernacular>

wounded at the siege of Grave, fighting under General Norrice (p. 16); or the cure of Master Bucland of Reading who had been under the care of an ignorant blood-letting quack (p. 31); or the cure of the man thrust through the body with a sword (p. 79). These cases have the merit of being at once interesting and informative and of throwing light on Clowes' methods and his mind.

Of less importance than the case studies but of considerable interest to the lay reader are the supplemental illustrations (pp. 140-144). Here are engravings of The Surgery Chest—probably the chest that Clowes carried with him in the Low Countries and in the sea fight against the Armada—with an elaborate background of soldiers engaged in battle. Then follow cuts of the various curious instruments which the “chirurgeons” of the sixteenth century obviously used in performing operations.

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The *Observations* show that Clowes was a well-informed man. He was familiar with the leading surgeons of the time both in England and on the continent, and he was widely read in his field. He says he made Calmathius “as it were a day-starre or Christallin clear looking-glasse.” Tagaltius (p. 179), Guido, Vigo (p. 170), and Quercetanus were his other chief text books. He shows familiarity with the works of Paracelsus and of Ambroise Paré, to whom he pays tribute more than once. He had read also seventeen English authors on medicine, most of whom are listed in his “Admonition to the Friendly Reader” (p. 225). Clowes set great store on reading and keeping himself informed and he urged others to read. Concluding his account of the young surgeon who had not been successful in treating a patient for gunpowder burn, Clowes writes:

then I spake little to him, but willed him to be more diligent in reading of good authors, and hereafter to be careful how he applied his medicine (p. 5).

A few of the more specific references in the *Observations* are worthy of note, as “Doctor Foster, a most learned gentleman, Reader of the Chirurgery lecture in the Physitians College in London (p. 73).” “I must needes say Master Banister for his knowledge and judgement in the Art, and for publishing certaine bookes of Surgerie in the English toong, deserveth double honor and praise of all men (p. 125).” “Master Balthrop late Sergeant Surgeon unto hir Maiestie being a man of a rare and exquisite experience in Chirurgerie: one in whom the olde proverbe might very well be verified, that is, To have a Lions Hart, a Ladies hand, and a Haukes eie, and what else is required in a good Surgeon was truly found in him (p. 127).” Throughout his book Clowes shows a fine generosity toward his colleagues. For the “quacksalvers,” however, he has the utmost scorn. These bring into disrepute what the author likes to call the noble art of surgery.

The *Observations* show not only a wide range of reading on his subject and an extensive acquaintance with contemporary surgeons, but, more important, they reveal in Clowes an inquiring mind, keen observation, and a willingness to learn by experiment. At St. Bartholomew's, for example, he introduced a new styptic powder which caused smaller sloughs than that of Gale, which it supplanted. At Arnhem he tried with success a new balm on a pike-wound seven

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inches long. The experimental attitude, eagerness to learn from other members of his craft, English and continental, and a modern spirit of inquiry runs through the pages of the *Observations*.

Had Clowes kept a daily record or diary of his professional life (1563-1604) he could have made wondrous revelations for the historian, the sociologist, and the man of letters. What he could have recorded of his experiences in Saint Bartholomew's Hospital and Christ's Hospital; of the expedition with the Earl of Warwick in France; with the Earl of Leicester in the Lowlands, where Sidney fell; with the fleet against the Armada! Clowes' was a full life as befits an Elizabethan. And though his *Observations*, concerned primarily with his professional work, is hardly a day to day record of the spacious times, it is incidentally revealing as to the daily life. For example, many of the patients whom Clowes treats through a period of years are soldiers or sailors, and one gets the impression of almost continuous conflict. And the "pomp and circumstance of glorious war" and adventure tend to disappear as we see the victims through the eyes of the surgeon. Vivid are the details concerning the soldier sent to Clowes for treatment, January 12, 1591. The man was suffering from a wound in the leg made by a poisonous arrow on the coast of Brazil. He and others had gone ashore to seek fresh water and were ambushed by the natives. In this account (pp. 22-24) is a vivid flash of the life of the Elizabethan explorers. Other realistic accounts are those of the seafaring men afflicted with the scurvy (p. 40), and the master of a Hoy who had both legs broken by a shot from a sea rover³⁹ only ten miles from London (p. 75).

Of the incidents in the book which reflect more particularly life in London, we cite only two. One is the falling down of the gallery at a bear garden, resulting in the injury of many people and the death of some (p. 68). Among the injured was a man with a fractured skull and a fractured thigh bone, who was brought to Clowes for treatment. The next episode may be given in brief in the author's own words:

Not long since, a certain Clothier, with two of his neighbors and freends, early in the morning, betweene fower [four] and five of the clocke, did take their journey from London, towards the countrey where they did dwell: they had not
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travelled fully two miles, but they were set upon by theeves and robbers, who wounded this man very dangerously and there he was taken, but his neighbors being better horsed, and also cowardly minded, for very feare they ran away, and so carried their owne and his money with them, being about some fower hundred pounds (pp. 85-86).

It is an interesting coincidence that the robbery at Gadshill, recounted in the anonymous play of *The Famous Victories of Henry V* and more elaborately in Shakespeare's *The First Part of Henry the Fourth* (II, i and ii), should have so many elements in common with Clowes' account. The time of day-between three and four in the morning the proximity to London, the amount of money involved, the running away of the cowardly from the scene of the robbery are common elements in the two accounts. Without ascribing indebtedness of the dramatist to Clowes we may state that the surgeon's narrative supports the realism of the Gadshill robbery.

39 https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/sea_rover

As to Clowes' style in the *Observations*, we may say that the author was at his best when writing narrative. In a sense this is fortunate so far as this book is concerned. The case histories are clear and interesting. The diction is simple and free from affectation, the phrasing is rhythmical, and the details are marshaled in orderly fashion. Though some of the sentences are quite lengthy, they are generally clear. These qualities are exemplified in the passage quoted above on the robbery of a "certaine Clothier," and in the account of Henry Battey, the cheesemonger (p. 22).

In exposition, however, Clowes' style is not so felicitous.⁴⁰ We have to remember that prose as an instrument of clear and precise explanation had not yet developed in England. This task remained for such writers as Dryden, Addison, and Steele, and others a century later. Though Clowes writes as well as the average author in his time and occasionally has vigorous prose exposition, he too frequently falls into hazy writing, the result in part of overloading his sentences. The manner which serves him well in narrative too often obscures his meaning in expository writing. Characteristic of this overloading and consequent complexity in structure and haziness in meaning is the sentence (p. 16) beginning ("As I have before said") and

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continuing for fifteen lines. The reader can scarcely keep in mind all of the details and their relationship, to the end of the sentence. Generally, Clowes' language is most vigorous when he writes with emotion as in the description of the "cosoning quacksalver (p. 66)."

The second treatise in this volume is concerned with the Lues Venerea, or French disease. Like the *Observations*, this discourse is based on the author's own experience, supplemented with information from other physicians. It is not, like the *Observations*, a series of case histories though the author introduces a number of concrete illustrations. After a brief account of the beginning and history of Lues Venerea and its prevalence throughout the world, Clowes explains the symptoms and prescribes remedies. On the medical aspects of this tract, Dr. Leake has ample comment.

It remains to say a word of the style. In style the tract on Lues Venerea differs little from the *Observations*. The writing is fluent, sometimes wordy; the sentences are occasionally awkward in structure, and too frequently overladen, as in the first sentence on Mercurie Diaphoreticum (p. 198). Some sentences taken out of their context do not make sense, as this one: "But even in the love of my countreymen, partly to admonish them to amend their lives, and partly to help the good people that be infected by eating and drinking, or keeping company unawares with those diseased persons: which either for shame, dare not bewray it, or for lacke of good Surgeons know not how to remedy it, or for lacke of abilitie, are not able otherwise to provide for the cure of it (p. 150)." Read in its context, this sentence has a definite meaning. Indeed Clowes seems to have made himself clear to his contemporaries, and with a little effort the modern reader may follow this author with much interest and profit.

As a successful physician and surgeon in his day, Clowes has a distinct place in the history of medicine. His inquiring mind, his eagerness to learn from observation and experience, his generosity to his colleagues, his willingness to collaborate with them for

40 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/felicitous>

the good of his patients and for the welfare of his country mark Clowes as a man who set an excellent example for his successors in the “noble art” of surgery.

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MEDICAL INTRODUCTION

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Since the Renaissance, the chief medical problems associated with wars have been the handling of gunshot wounds, the management of powder burns, and the treatment of venereal disease. In the midst of World War II the bulk of medical interest is still on these three problems, in spite of the increasing importance of the control of infectious and exotic diseases and the prevention of neuropsychiatric disturbances.

Medicine in war is intensely practical. Under the stimulus of the necessities of caring for battle injuries and wounds, extra emphasis is naturally assumed by the special field of surgery. The internist and the psychiatrist have only recently come to play an important part in war medicine as a result of increasing appreciation of the natural causes of infectious and functional diseases, and of mental disorder. Up to this century the chief medical works relating to war were written by surgeons, who were the ones mostly concerned about the matter.

William Clowes' Position As A Surgeon

The ancient art of surgery, originating in the practical demands for care of the injured, had declined during the scholastic period as a result of unfortunate interpretations of church decrees. Modern surgery, like so many other features of our culture, developed in the iconoclastic attitude of the 15th and 16th centuries. Discovery of ancient manuscripts of classical writers such as Hippocrates and Galen raised doubts regarding traditional scholastic teachings. Andreas Vesalius (1514-1561) dramatically demonstrated the structure of the human body (*De Humani Corporis Fabrica*, Basle, 1543), and showed how it differs from what the scholastics had thought. The new anatomical learning was brilliantly applied to successful surgical practice in the field by Ambroise Paré (1510-1590) in his *La methode de traicter* (Paris, 1545), and in later writings.

Paré's practical success made surgery at once respectable and significant. His writings, like those of his German contemporaries, were immensely popular with the new kind of practical physician whose services were as much in demand then as now. In England, Thomas Gale (1507-1586) followed Paré in denying the poisonous

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effect of bullets, but probably contributed more harm than help with his fondness for recommending messy ointments for wounds (*An Excellent Treatise of Wounds Made with Gonneshot*, London, 1563). Thomas Vicary, an articulate English surgeon who died in 1562, had become the first Master of the United Company of Barbers and Surgeons, which had been incorporated by Act of Parliament in 1540. His writings (*The Englishman's Treasure*, London, 1548?-1577), while well-known, were not especially influential. English surgery lagged behind that practiced on the continent and imitated it in theory, technique and instrumentation. This status persisted until the period of the Hunters.

Probably in the same year that the Barber Surgeons' Company was established, William Clowes was born. He is generally reputed to be the greatest of the Elizabethan surgeons. This reputation would seem to derive more from the lusty style of his writing than from the technical quality of his surgery. His first service was with the Earl of Warwick's army at Le Havre. In 1575 he was on the staff of St. Bartholomew's Hospital, and later served as a fleet surgeon against the Armada. Following this, he was appointed Surgeon to the Queen. Professor Starnes has well reviewed what little is known of the details of Clowes' career.

Sir William Osler, who popularized current interest in medical history, noted Norman Moore's estimate of Clowes: "His books are the best surgical writings of his time in English. He had read a great deal, but trusted much to his own observation, and his modern spirit of inquiry makes his pages different from the compilations of his friends Baker and Banister. He always speaks with generosity of his professional contemporaries, and his books are full of pictures of daily life in the reign of Elizabeth. His son William (1582-1648) was surgeon to Charles I."

Let it be clear at once that Clowes was not a significant contributor to medical progress. He was a competent and honest surgeon who followed the practices popularized by Paré and Paracelsus, and already well established by Fabry, Brunschwig, Gerstorff, and Wurtz. The success of surgical procedures at the time was, of course, handicapped by lack of knowledge of the cause of sepsis. Similarly, there

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was no recognition of the principle that a burn is essentially a large, open wound. In order to handle burns successfully we now know that it is essential to prevent infection, to maintain fluid balance, and to keep light pressure on the area. Most surgeons of the period followed Paré's injunctions to keep wounds clean, to avoid cauterizing with boiling oil, and to use splints, braces, and casts to immobilize injured parts.

Clowes apparently followed Paré's example and pursued a conservative course reasonable for the knowledge of his time. He engaged in the current discussion on the possible poisonous character of gunshot wounds, and he experimented on the problem of poisoned bullets. While his twenty-eight case reports are fairly clear, he failed to preserve Paré's objectivity and freely indulged in hardy Elizabethan expletive.

However, William Clowes was one of the first great English medical teachers. By lecture, precept, and writing, he stimulated his colleagues in the Barber Surgeons' Company to do their best. As Harvey Graham indicates, Clowes never achieved the eminence of Paré, but like him helped to make his colleagues and successors realize that surgery is essentially a simple art, "which would not be advanced by confining it to the Latin tongue or by regarding it as a mystery and shrouding it in secrecy."

Clowes' Best Book

In 1588 Clowes published "A Prooved Practise for all Young Chirurgians Concerning Burnings with Gun Powder and Wounds Made with Gunshot" (T. Orwyn for T. Cadman, London). This was expanded and in a second edition appeared in 1596, in the form reproduced in the present volume. The treatise on gunshot wounds is

lengthened beyond its essential surgical requirements by an extraordinary number of complex and elaborate prescriptions for ointments and lotions. The portion on gunshot wounds closes on page 137, to be followed by “Certaine precepts Meet for yoong students in Chirurgerie, gathered chiefly out of Guido Decauliaco by William Clowes.” This comprises two pages of interesting iambic heptametric verse, probably original with Clowes. It is followed by several pages of illustrations of surgical instruments. On page 145 occurs a

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separate title page for “A Briefe and Necessarie Treatise, Touching The Cure Of The Disease Now Usually called Lues Venerea.” From page 226 to 229 is added a special treatise “The nature and propertie of Quicksilver, by G. Baker one of hir Maiesites Chirurgions.”

One would think that G. Baker must have been a friend and colleague of Clowes to have had his article appended to Clowes’ book. One of Elizabeth’s surgeons was, in fact, a George Baker. At any rate, Clowes was not above quarreling with him, even as medical men do still, although perhaps with not so great physical violence. In 1577 the Court of Barber Surgeons, as shown in its records, pardoned Clowes’ offense in fighting in the fields with George Baker. Perhaps they got into a row over some patient or over some professional problem.

One of the chief problems for the surgeons of those times was whether or not gunshot wounds were of poisonous nature. Paré’s skill and cleanliness had shown that most gunshot wounds would heal satisfactorily if properly cleaned and drained and if the bullet were extracted. Clowes indeed had so been taught. Clowes felt that the heat of explosion would render harmless a bullet treated with poison, but direct experiments indicated to him that the heat of explosion was not sufficient to burn off material that might have been placed on bullets. He remained convinced that an ordinary bullet would not poison a wound, in accord with Paré and Gale, but he felt that bullets might be smeared with poisons in order definitely to produce death.

This and other controversial matters with respect to handling gunshot wounds might have prompted Clowes to write his book. In general, his writings show strong common sense and give evidence of his surgical skill. However, **there is no significant addition made by Clowes to the general discussion on surgical principles in progress at the time.**

While Clowes’ volume contains illustrations of surgical instruments, they are not distinguished from similar illustrations to be found in other surgical books of the period. The first notable printed illustrations of surgical instruments were made by Hieronymus Brunschwig (1450-1533) in his *Wundartzny* (Strassburg, 1497), and these seem to have been copied by subsequent surgical writers for a couple of centuries.

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No important advances in surgical instruments had yet been made since Roman times, to judge from comparison of these illustrations with recovered Roman surgical instruments. However, Clowes’ book contains an illustration of a surgical field chest for use under war conditions (p. 140). Clowes also gives a long list of unguents, pills, plasters, oils, and instruments (pp. 104-110) which were to be carried by the surgeon

who might “follow the wars either by sea or land.” The statement is frequently made, as by F. H. Garrison and L. T. Morton in their *Medical Bibliography* (London, 1943), that Wilhelm Fabry (Fabricius Hildanus, 1560-1634) was the first to describe a field drug-chest for army use in his *Feldt Arztny Buch* (Basle, 1615). Clearly, Clowes anticipated Fabry, but Clowes’ advice probably was compiled from his older contemporaries.

The full story of 16th century surgery has been told in the many published appreciations of Paré, excepting perhaps what may yet be learned of Daza, Paré’s Spanish contemporary (J. B. deC. M. Saunders, *Essays in Biology in Honor of Herbert M. Evans*, University of California, 1943).

Clowes’ interest in elaborate prescriptions for dressings and ointments merits special comment. The use of drugs in medicine obviously began by astute observation of the effects of taking into the body various plant, animal and mineral materials in the search for food. The general over-all effects of such materials would be noted, together with soothing or irritating actions that they might have when applied to the skin. The obvious step then is to apply such observation and knowledge to the correction of conditions that might result in injury or disease. Thus a plant found to cause purgative action would rather naturally be thought of for use when an individual might be constipated. This rather rational procedure developed very early in various parts of the world among native peoples, and reached a considerable state of formal development in ancient Egypt. The Ebers Medical Papyrus, written about 1500 B. C., is a textbook containing many hundred recipes which have been found by experience to be useful for alleviating disease conditions. Similarly, the Hearst Medical Papyrus, of about the same period, is a practicing physician’s notebook of recipes collected from various sources for use on patients when a diagnosis had been reached.

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In these ancient documents each prescription, it would appear, had originally a single ingredient. However, several such prescriptions might be indicated for the relief of the same conditions. In subsequent copying, scribes simply lumped the ingredients together, since there was no indication as to which might be preferable. Thus arose the complex prescriptions introduced by the Greco-Romans into the medieval period, and elaborated by the Arabs. These were reintroduced into Europe after the Crusades and were copied from one author to another for hundreds of years.

Many of the prescriptions noted by Clowes came from continental sources, which traced back to the school of Salerno in the thirteenth century in Italy, and thus back through Arab compilers through Greco-Roman times, and from such writers as Galen and his predecessors, to earlier Egyptian originals.

Clowes’ messy unguents seem to have been immediately derived from his older English contemporary, Thomas Gale (1507-1586), whose *Excellent Treatise of Wounds Made with Gonneshot* (London, 1563), recommends many complex ointments for wounds similar to those described by Clowes.

Doctor Starnes has well discussed Clowes’ use of the vernacular. It is interesting that Clowes felt it necessary to use Latin for his prescriptions. He was probably required

to do so by the regulations of the College of Physicians. Prescriptions in the vernacular were considered to be improper in a professional book. If the volume were to fall in the hands of an unscrupulous layman it might result in quackery or at the least in self-medication. Both of these matters were to be condemned by the properly licensed physician.

Clowes' writings contain many references to the excellent Guido. This was Guy de Chauliac, who was born near Auvergne, France, in the latter part of the 13th century. Guy obtained his medical degree at Montpellier and studied later at Bologna and Paris. He came to Avignon in 1348 in the service of Pope Clement VI. He remained in Avignon and there wrote his "Great Surgery" in 1363, first printed in Lyon in 1478. The volume covers all important fields of surgery and remained the leading surgical text for several centuries.

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In this volume are described the tenaculæ of Avicenna (980-1037), which are serrated and half-moon shaped, for the withdrawal of arrows or other fixed bodies, such as shown by Clowes on page 141 of his "Booke." Clowes also reproduces the dilating scissors (p. 141) described by Guy de Chauliac for opening the flesh in order to extract more readily arrowheads or other similar bodies. Pictured in Clowes' volume (p. 142, erroneously numbered 133) is the serrated and beaked tenaculæ of Albucasis (1030-1106), as described by Guy de Chauliac. These instruments, of course, had been previously depicted in surgical volumes preceding those of Clowes.

That portion of Guy de Chauliac's work relating to wounds and fractures has been attractively translated and annotated by W. A. Brennan (*Guy de Chauliac On Wounds and Fractures*, Chicago, 1923).

Clowes' regard for Guy de Chauliac is shown by his elaborate versification of Guy's general precepts for surgeons. These are rather simply stated by Guy in his introduction: "The conditions necessary for the surgeon are four: first, he should be learned; second, he should be expert; third, he must be ingenious, and fourth, he should be able to adapt himself." Guy goes on to say that the surgeon should be gracious to the sick, considerate to his associates, and cautious in his prognostications. "Let him be modest, dignified, gentle, pitiful, and merciful, not covetous nor an extortionist of money; but rather let his reward be according to his work, to the means of the patient, to the quality of the issue, and to his own dignity." Clowes amplifies these sentiments in his rhymed couplets and obviously takes considerable liberty in adapting them to his purposes. But Clowes' verses have a peculiar appeal of their own.

Clowes' Treatise on Venereal Disease

As Clowes relates, in December, 1494, there was recognized by physicians first, and then by everyone else, that a hitherto little-known severe disease had broken out among the French soldiers participating in the siege of Naples. The disease was called by the French, *Morbus Neapolitanus*, but the Neapolitans called it *Morbus Gallicus*. The common name, *syphilis*, developed through the popularity of that extraordinary medical poem by Girolamo Fracastoro (1478-1553),

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the genial Veronese physician, astronomer and poet, Syphilis sive *MORBUS GALLICUS*, which appeared in Verona in August, 1530.

The leading character in Fracastoro's poem was named Syphilis, and so well did the author describe the symptoms and treatment of the disease in his hero, that his name was attached to the disease itself. The term used by Clowes, *Lues Venerea*, the more general "venereal plague," became gradually shortened until the word Lues became synonymous with *syphilis*.

In general Clowes' account follows the major descriptions of the sixteenth century with regard to the newly recognized disease. It is, however, more practical and to the point than the majority of discussions. Clowes follows Paré. In the realistic French surgeon, Clowes found a worthy inspiration for his own practical venture. In discussing the venereal plague Clowes wastes no time in speculation as to its origin.

Such speculations have aroused bitter controversy. Since the disease was first recognized by European physicians shortly after the return of the sailors of Columbus from the second voyage to the New World, it was generally believed that the disease was imported from America. However, in spite of the lack of definite pre-Columbian bony evidences of syphilis, there is good evidence to show that the "large pox" was known in Europe and the East before the voyages of Columbus. Indeed one of the best remedies for syphilis, namely, mercury, had already been developed by the Arabs for use against the "large pox" as early as the tenth century. When the venereal plague was first recognized in Europe, mercury ointments were used immediately with great success.

The temptation of pushing treatment too vigorously with mercury resulted inevitably in toxic reactions. Many syphilitic patients complained that the treatment was worse than the disease.

The disease had spread like wildfire. It probably had been dormant for a long while and may easily have been given new virulence by introduction from the New World of a related micro-organism causing a similar disease, "yaws," which, however, is not venereal.

The abuses of mercury promptly led to efforts to find other methods of treatment. Elaborate theoretical discussions regarding the qualities of humors in the disease brought varying opinions regarding

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the value of sweating, purging, bleeding, and the use of various drug decoctions. On the theory that wherever a disease occurs naturally, there will also be found drugs for its treatment, many new drugs were introduced from the New World for use against the disease. The chief drugs of this sort were china root, so ably discussed by Vesalius (1546), smilax, sassafras, sarsaparilla, and guaiacum. Decoctions were usually made from the roots of these plants and drunk in copious quantities. There is no evidence that any of these plant preparations had the slightest effect in syphilis. Yet they themselves produced no harm, and since the disease tends to be self-limiting they may have given the appearance of producing some benefit.

Clowes properly emphasizes the value of quicksilver. However, there was no need for him to indulge in such complicated descriptions for its use. Simple mercury ointments well rubbed into the skin are still effective therapy for syphilis. The elaborate prescriptions, with careful directions for their preparation, may have helped greatly in giving the patient the idea that a great deal of care and trouble was needed to carry out an effective cure. Clowes followed the general practice of his time in prescribing elaborately for the purging, the dieting, and the general care of his patient. A great deal of this may have involved the idea of penitence as punishment for the implied pleasure in contracting the disease.

The auxiliary prescriptions recommended by Clowes contain many remedies still utilized for various purposes he proposed. Senna, colocynth, and liquorice are still commonly used as purgatives. Turpentine, camphor and myrrh can still be used as antiseptic irritants. Cantharides produces kidney irritation. Anise, pepper, ginger, cinnamon, and other spices produce stomach and intestinal movement. However, most of these anciently used drugs have been superseded by chemicals which are more easily controlled and more specifically useful for particular effects desired by the physician.

There was no need for Clowes to differentiate between the venereal plague and gonorrhoea. Gonorrhoea, the gleet or clap, was prevalent enough, but no one seemed to pay much attention to it. It was not considered to be much more serious than a "cold" and probably was just about as common. The really serious venereal plague in Clowes' time was syphilis. It produced severe symptoms and often caused death.

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General concern over its importance is indicated by the great number of volumes about it which appeared in the sixteenth century. Practically every medical man of any consequence had to write about it.

Summary

In summarizing Clowes' position in medicine, it must be emphasized that he was not a major contributor. He was an excellent practical surgeon who wrote honestly from his own experience but whose ideas were largely taken from relatively standardized procedures of his time. He probably performed a great service for his colleagues in writing for them in the vernacular.

It is interesting that many centuries after Clowes we are still concerned with the medical problems which were so vital to him. The accumulation of precise knowledge regarding ourselves in health and in sickness is a slow process. While we think we are much better equipped than Clowes to handle war wounds or venereal disease, we still must strive mightily to apply our knowledge effectively to the accomplishment of our purposes. From the honesty and earnestness of Clowes we may still derive great stimulus.

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